

How Does SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Rapid Test Kit Work?

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Brief Immunology Background

When a pathogen, such as viruses (like SARS-CoV-2), invades the body and infect host cells, a multifaceted cascade of immune responses is activated involving different cells types, including B cells. The main role of B cells is the production of antibodies with specific affinity to components (antigens) of the invading pathogen. Activated B cells undergo differentiation process and become plasma cells. Plasma cells produce and secrete large amount of antigen-specific antibodies, also called immunoglobulins, which bind to their specific antigens resulting in the neutralization of the invading pathogen.

Humans have five classes/isotypes of antibodies: IgA, IgD, IgE, IgG and IgM (Ig stands for immunoglobulin).

The secretory IgA (sIgA) represents the hallmark of mucosal immunity, it provides protection against pathogen replication and shedding within the mucosal surfaces of for example the respiratory/airway tract (such as nose and throat).

IgG and IgM are the most abundant antibodies in human serum, accounting for 75-85% and 5-10% of all immunoglobulins respectively. While IgG is secreted as a single molecule (monomer), secreted IgM antibodies are large pentamer molecules (made of five individual IgM antibodies) with multiple antigen binding sites (see illustration in figure 1).

IgM is the first antibody secreted upon infection/exposure to foreign antigens, reaching maximum concentration at ~8 days, followed by a gradual decrease until reaching almost undetectable levels ~3 weeks post-infection (illustrated in figure 1).

Figure 1: Simplified illustration of the kinetic of IgM and IgG production upon infection or exposure to an antigen (doesn't reflect the kinetic of antibody production against SARS-CoV-2).

IgG secretion begins around ~ day 8 post-infection/antigen exposure, reaching maximum concentration after ~2 to 4 weeks (illustrated in figure 1), followed by a slowly decrease in a time frame that depends on several factors. **IgG antibodies are responsible for long-term immunity and immunological memory.** The immunity will last as long as a sufficient amount of effective IgG antibodies against the pathogen persists. IgG antibodies can persist for several months or years. For COVID-19, ongoing and future studies will reveal how long IgG antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 are persistent upon infection and/or vaccination.

SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Rapid Test Kit

Figure 2: Illustration of the IgM/IgG immunochromatographic strip assay which can be applied for any antigen/pathogen of interest. The assembled pads/strips are encased inside a plastic device, which is not show in this illustration.

SARS-CoV-2 antibody rapid test kit utilizes the techniques of chromatography (separation of a mixture) and qualitative immunoassay (measures the presence of molecules of interest through the use of antibodies and/or antigens), to detect the presence of IgM and IgG against SARS-CoV-2 antigens in a very small volume of blood or serum (~20 μ l blood; ~10 μ l serum). A finger prick whole blood is sufficient to perform the test. Some kits are designed to detect also IgA.

A typical SARS-CoV-2 antibody rapid test device is composed of (illustrated in figure 2):

- 1. Plastic (PVC) backing card:** The PVC plate is used to back the test strip
- 2. A sample pad:** consists of cellulose absorbent fiber sheet (cellulosic filter paper), on which the sample (blood, serum) is applied, and enable absorption and lateral flow of the sample.
- 3. A conjugate pad:** consists of glass fiber sheet, on which labelled control non-human IgG antibodies and SARS-CoV-2 antigens are applied and transiently dried (are in a dehydrated state). The test kits use typically rabbit IgG or chicken IgG as control antibodies, and receptor binding domain (RBD) of the spike protein or the nucleocapsid protein of SARS-CoV-2 as antigens. The control antibodies and viral antigens are linked to colored particles (such as colloidal gold particles or latex microspheres), which enable the visualization of the analyte molecules that will bind to the antigens, and the antibodies that will capture the control antibodies.
- 4. Test or Capture pad:** consists of a nitrocellulose membrane, on which antibodies are separately immobilized in distinct zones, to form three distinct antibody capture lines:
 - The control zone:** coated with species-specific anti-IgG antibodies which bind to the control non-human IgG antibodies.
 - The IgG test zone:** coated with anti-human IgG antibodies which bind to the human IgG antibodies.
 - The IgM test zone:** coated with anti-human IgM antibodies which bind to the human IgM antibodies.The nitrocellulose membrane pad is attached to the middle of the PVC backing plate. The conjugate pad is attached to the edge of the nitrocellulose membrane with few millimetres overlap, and the sample pad is attached to the edge of the conjugate pad with few millimetres overlap.
- 5. An absorbent pad:** consists of a layer (or layers) of cellulose absorbent paper, which are placed at the distal end of the test strip. The role of the absorbent pad is to increase the draw of the sample across the reaction membrane by capillary action (the process of a liquid to flow in narrow spaces - capillary tubes - of a solid material without the assistance of external forces like gravity). The absorbent pad is attached to the edge of the nitrocellulose membrane with few millimetres overlap.

Principle of The SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Assay

The SARS-CoV-2 antibody assay is based on immunochromatography, initially developed for the determination of pregnancy on spot (Paek et al., 2000).

When the sample (blood, serum, or other specimen) is added onto the sample pad of the test strip, and dissolved by adding an aqueous medium, the liquid phase (dissolved sample) moves forward and enter into the conjugate pad.

Figure 3: Illustration of the workflow of the IgM/IgG immunochromatographic strip assay.

When the sample liquid reaches the conjugate pad, if it contains antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, they will bind to the labelled antigens of SARS-CoV-2.

Then the antibody-antigen complexes, along with the hydrated labelled control antibodies, leave the conjugation pad and flow continuously through the capture pad via capillary action, until they are captured by the immobilized antibodies on the nitrocellulose membrane. The IgM zone of the nitrocellulose membrane will capture human IgM antibodies. The IgG zone of the

nitrocellulose membrane will capture human IgG antibodies. The control zone of the nitrocellulose membrane will capture the control IgG antibodies.

The capture of antibodies by the respective zones of the nitrocellulose membrane results in colored visible band(s). The visible color is a result of accumulation of labelled antigens or control antibodies in the appropriate test zone.

Interpretation of The Antibody Assay Results

The assay can be considered as succeeded only if the control zone shows a clear colored band. If a colored band does not appear in the control zone, the test result is invalid, and the sample needs to be tested again (illustrated in figure 2).

Figure 4: Illustration of all possible results of the IgM/IgG immunochromatographic strip assay.

- 1. Single positive result for IgM:** A clear colored line in the IgM zone, with no visible band in the IgG zone, indicates that the sample (e.g. blood or serum) contains only IgM antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, and thus the tested person has an active infection or was infected or vaccinated just recently.
- 2. Double positive result:** A clear colored line in both, the IgG and IgM zones, indicates that the sample (e.g. blood or serum) contains IgG and IgM antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, and thus the tested person has developed antibodies against the virus upon a recent infection or vaccination. Positivity for both, IgG and IgM, indicates an increasing immunity from a current/recent infection.
- 3. Single positive result for IgG:** A clear colored line in the IgG zone, with no visible band in the IgM zone, indicates that the sample (e.g. blood or serum) contains only IgG antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, and thus the infection or vaccination of the tested person occurred in the past, the infection is no more active.

Remarks

- 1.** Hitherto the SARS-CoV-2 antibody rapid test kit doesn't allow to evaluate the protection from COVID-19. The kit doesn't perform qualitative assay, it doesn't measure how

strong the antibody response is, neither whether the detected antibodies are able to neutralize the virus effectively, nor how long the antibodies will persist.

2. Asymptomatic infections may test positive.
3. Even if you have developed antibodies against SARS-CoV-2, you still need to follow the protective measures (such as masks, hand washing, physical distancing, etc.), because you could still be infected and transmit the virus to vulnerable people. In addition, you could be infected by mutant SARS-CoV-2 variants, against which the antibodies developed during the previous infection/vaccination are not effective.